

Halogenated 4-aryloxymethylcoumarins as potent antimicrobial agents

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Abstract : Halogenated phenols reacted with various 4-bromomethylcoumarins to furnish the corresponding 4-aryloxymethylcoumarins. Introduction of chloro and methoxy groups in the coumarin ring elicited considerable antimicrobial activity against *B. subtilis*, *E. coli*, *A. niger* and *C. albicans*. In the aryloxy moiety, the chloro group as a substituent were found to be more active than the corresponding bromo compounds. The growth inhibition was observed even at concentrations of less than 10 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ in some cases.

Keywords : 4-Chloro/bromo phenoxymethylcoumarins, synthesis, antimicrobial.

Introduction

Natural products containing chloro and bromo substituents have been found to exhibit insecticidal and fungicidal activities¹. Polyhalogenated marine natural products have recently been reported to exhibit selective toxicity towards cancer cells². Chlorinated aromatic hydrocarbons and phenols are well known antibacterial agents^{3,4}. The wide ranging biological properties exhibited by both naturally occurring and synthetic coumarins⁵⁻⁷ have prompted us to investigate various 4-aryloxymethylcoumarins containing bio-compatible fragments like paracetamol⁸ and vanillin⁹ as potential antiinflammatory and antimicrobial agents. In view of this, it was contemplated to generate various 4-aryloxymethylcoumarins with polyhalogenated groups and to study their antimicrobial properties.

Results and discussion

The required 4-bromomethylcoumarins¹⁰ **1** was synthesized by the Pechmann cyclisation of various phenols with ethyl 4-bromoacetoacetate using sulphuric acid as the condensing agent. 4-Bromo, 2,4-dichloro, 2,4,5-trichloro and 2,4,6-tribromophenols were employed as nucleophiles under standard acetone-potassium carbonate conditions. The reactions were complete in 24 h at room temperature. The time required for the completion of the

reactions was almost independent of the number of halogen atoms present in the phenolic moiety (Scheme 1).

In the IR spectrum of compound 6-methyl-4-(2',4',6'-tribromophenoxymethyl)chromen-2-one **5a**, the lactone carbonyl stretching frequency was observed at 1721 cm^{-1} . In the ¹H NMR (300 MHz) (DMSO-*d*₆) spectrum of compound **5a**, a singlet each at δ 2.50 (3H), 5.29 (2H) and 6.67 (1H) was observed due to C₆-CH₃, C₄-CH₂ and C₃-H protons, respectively. The C₅-H of coumarin appeared as a doublet at δ 7.63, *J*_{meta} 3.3 Hz. The C₇-H of coumarin was observed as a doublet of doublet at δ 7.35, *J*_{ortho} 8.4 Hz and *J*_{meta} 3.3 Hz. The C₈-H of coumarin was observed as a doublet at δ 7.47, *J*_{ortho} 8.4 Hz. The protons H-3' and H-5' in the aryloxy moiety appeared as a singlet at δ 8.03 (2H).

The mass spectra of the 6-methyl products **2a**, **3a**, **4a**, **4g** and **5a** have shown that the molecular ion-peaks and the relative intensities observed were in agreement with the number of halogens present¹¹. A brief generalized mass spectral fragmentation for ethers **2a**, **3a**, **4a** and **5a** is given in Scheme 2, which shows that the base peak is observed at *m/z* 145 in all the cases by the initial homolytic cleavage of the CH₂-O bond and subsequent loss of carbon monoxide. This is in accordance with the established fragmentation pattern for coumarins¹².

a, R = 6-CH₃; b, R = 7-CH₃; c, R = 5,6-benzo; d, R = 7,8-benzo; e, R = 6-OCH₃; f, R = 6-Cl; g, R = 6-Br; X = 2',4'-dichloro; 2',4',5'-trichloro; 4'-bromo; 2',4',6'-tribromo

Scheme 1

In vitro antimicrobial activity :

The standard strains were procured from the microbial type culture collection and Gene Bank (MTCC), Institute of Microbial Technology, Chandigarh, India. The

antibacterial and antifungal activities of the synthesized compounds were performed against the following bacterial strains : *Bacillus subtilis* (MTCC 297) and *Escherichia coli* (MTCC 1089) and the following fungal strains : *Aspergillus niger* and *Candida albicans* by broth micro dilution method^{13,14}. For antibacterial assay, Ciprofloxacin was used as the standard, whereas Gresiofulvin was used as the standard in antifungal assays.

In vitro antibacterial assay :

The antibacterial activities (Table 1) of 2e, 2f, 3a, 3e, 3f and 4f (MIC : ≤ 10 µg ml⁻¹) were comparable to that of Ciprofloxacin (MIC : 8 µg ml⁻¹) against *B. subtilis*. Compounds 2e-g, 3b, 3e, 3f and 4f (MIC : ≤ 10 µg ml⁻¹) were found to be weakly active against *E. coli* in comparison to Ciprofloxacin (MIC : 4 µg ml⁻¹). In general, an increase in the number of chlorine or bromine atoms in the aryloxy moiety has increased the antibacterial activity of the compounds.

The results from the antifungal study (Table 1) showed that all the chlorinated ethers 2a-g, 3b and 3f exhibited significant antifungal activity (MIC : 10–25 µg ml⁻¹) against *A. niger* in comparison to Gresiofulvin (MIC : 50 µg ml⁻¹). Compounds 3a, 3c, 3d and 3g (MIC : 50 µg ml⁻¹) are equipotent to Gresiofulvin (MIC : 50 µg ml⁻¹) against *A. niger*. Compounds 2a-g and 3a-g (MIC : 10–50 µg ml⁻¹) are more active against Gresiofulvin (MIC : 100 µg ml⁻¹) than against *C. albicans*. 6-CH₃, 6-OCH₃ and 6-Cl group in the coumarin moiety has increased the antifungal activity but an increase in the number of chlorine atoms in the aryloxy moiety has not increased their antifungal activity.

In contrast, a number of compounds, 2a-g, 3a, 3g, 4g

Scheme 2

Note

Table 1. *In vitro* antibacterial and antifungal activity of the compounds (2a-5g) : MIC in $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$

Compd.	R	X	Bacteria		Fungi	
			<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>
2a	6-CH ₃	2',4'-dichloro	25	25	10	25
2b	7-CH ₃	2',4'-dichloro	25	50	25	50
2c	5,6-benzo	2',4'-dichloro	50	50	25	50
2d	7,8-benzo	2',4'-dichloro	50	50	25	50
2e	6-OCH ₃	2',4'-dichloro	< 10	10	10	10
2f	6-Cl	2',4'-dichloro	< 10	10	10	10
2g	6-Br	2',4'-dichloro	25	10	25	10
3a	6-CH ₃	2',4',5'-trichloro	10	25	50	25
3b	7-CH ₃	2',4',5'-trichloro	25	10	25	25
3c	5,6-benzo	2',4',5'-trichloro	25	50	50	50
3d	7,8-benzo	2',4',5'-trichloro	25	50	50	50
3e	6-OCH ₃	2',4',5'-trichloro	10	< 10	10	10
3f	6-Cl	2',4',5'-trichloro	< 10	10	10	10
3g	6-Br	2',4',5'-trichloro	25	25	50	50
4a	6-CH ₃	4'-bromo	50	50	100	100
4b	7-CH ₃	4'-bromo	50	50	100	100
4c	5,6-benzo	4'-bromo	50	50	100	100
4d	7,8-benzo	4'-bromo	50	50	100	100
4e	6-OCH ₃	4'-bromo	50	50	100	100
4f	6-Cl	4'-bromo	10	10	50	50
4g	6-Br	4'-bromo	25	50	100	100
5a	6-CH ₃	2',4',6'-tribromo	25	25	75	100
5b	7-CH ₃	2',4',6'-tribromo	25	25	75	100
5c	5,6-benzo	2',4',6'-tribromo	50	50	100	100
5d	7,8-benzo	2',4',6'-tribromo	50	50	100	100
5e	6-OCH ₃	2',4',6'-tribromo	25	25	50	100
5f	6-Cl	2',4',6'-tribromo	10	10	50	50
5g	6-Br	2',4',6'-tribromo	50	50	100	100
	Ciprofloxacin		8	4	-	-
	Gresiofulvin		-	-	50	100

MIC - Minimum Inhibitory Concentration.

and 5f were more active (MIC : 10-50 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) than Gresiofulvin (MIC : 100 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) against *A. niger*. Increase in the number of chlorine or bromine atoms increased antifungal activity against *A. niger* but caused no change against *C. albicans*.

Experimental

Melting points were determined using an electric melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectra were run in KBr pellets on a Nicolet Impact-410 FT-IR spectrometer (ν_{max} in cm^{-1}). ¹H NMR spectra were recorded in DMSO-*d*₆ with TMS as an internal standard (Chemical shift in δ , ppm *J* values in Hz) on a Bruker 300 MHz FT-NMR spectrometer. Mass spectra (EI) were recorded from Indian Institute of Chemical Technology, Hyderabad. Purity of the compounds was checked by TLC. Structures were drawn using ChemDraw Ultra version 6.0. All the reagents were of laboratory reagent quality and were purchased from S.D. Fine-chemicals Limited and

used after purification. All the new compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

General procedure for synthesis of halogenated-4-aryloxymethyl coumarins (2a-5g) :

Halogenated phenols (0.001 *M*) and anhydrous K₂CO₃ (1.38 g, 0.001 *M*) were stirred in dry acetone (25 ml) for 30 min. 4-Bromomethylcoumarins (0.001 *M*) were added and stirring was continued for 24 h. The reaction mixture was concentrated and poured into crushed ice. The solid separated was filtered and washed with 5% HCl (10 ml) to neutralize excess of potassium carbonate. Then, it was washed with water to free from acid and then with dilute ethanol. The crude product was dried and recrystallised from DMF.

4-(2',4'-Dichlorophenoxyethyl)-6-methylchromen-2-one (2a) :

Colorless crystals, yield 78%, m.p. 266-268 °C; ν_{max} 1709 (C=O) cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} 2.50 (3H, s, C₆-CH₃), 5.52 (2H,

s, CH₂O), 6.58 (1H, s, C₃-H), 7.33–7.70 (6H, m, Ar-H); *m/z* (%) 334 (M⁺, 30), 336 (M⁺+2, 20), 338 (M⁺+4, 6) (Found : C, 60.74; H, 3.42. C₁₇H₁₂O₃Cl₂ Calcd. : C, 60.92; H, 3.61%).

4-(2',4'-Dichlorophenoxyethyl)-7-methylchromen-2-one (2b) :

Colorless crystals, yield 76%, m.p. 230–232 °C; ν_{\max} 1731 (C=O) cm⁻¹; δ_{H} 2.43 (3H, s, C₆-CH₃), 5.30 (2H, s, CH₂O), 6.63 (1H, s, C₃-H), 7.07–7.52 (6H, m, Ar-H) (Found : C, 60.76; H, 3.41. C₁₇H₁₂O₃Cl₂ Calcd. : C, 60.92; H 3.61%).

1-(2',4'-Dichlorophenoxyethyl)-benzof[f]chromen-3-one (2c) :

Colorless crystals, yield 80%, m.p. 250–252 °C; ν_{\max} 1720 (C=O) cm⁻¹; δ_{H} 5.63 (2H, s, CH₂O), 6.99 (1H, s, C₃-H), 7.77–8.78 (9H, m, Ar-H) (Found : C, 64.36; H, 3.10. C₂₀H₁₂O₃Cl₂ Calcd. : C, 64.71; H, 3.26%).

4-(2',4'-Dichlorophenoxyethyl)-benzo[h]chromen-2-one (2d) :

Colorless crystals, yield 74%, m.p. 296–298 °C; ν_{\max} 1709 (C=O) cm⁻¹; δ_{H} 5.50 (2H, s, CH₂O), 6.84 (1H, s, C₃-H), 7.75–8.52 (9H, m, Ar-H) (Found : C, 64.38; H, 3.11. C₂₀H₁₂O₃Cl₂ Calcd. : C, 64.71; H, 3.26%).

4-(2',4'-Dichlorophenoxyethyl)-6-methoxychromen-2-one (2e) :

Colorless crystals, yield 70%, m.p. 240–242 °C; ν_{\max} 1718 (C=O) cm⁻¹; δ_{H} 3.98 (3H, s, C₆-OCH₃), 5.32 (2H, s, CH₂O), 6.35 (1H, s, C₃-H), 7.70–7.54 (6H, m, Ar-H) (Found : C, 58.01; H, 3.33. C₁₇H₁₂O₄Cl₂ Calcd. : C, 58.14; H, 3.44%).

6-Chloro-4-(2',4'-dichlorophenoxyethyl)-chromen-2-one (2f) :

Colorless crystals, yield 62%, m.p. 260–262 °C; ν_{\max} 1727 (C=O) cm⁻¹; δ_{H} 5.22 (2H, s, CH₂O), 6.80 (1H, s, C₃-H), 7.27–7.56 (6H, m, Ar-H) (Found : C, 53.89; H, 2.39. C₁₆H₉O₃Cl₃ Calcd. : C, 54.04; H, 2.55%).

6-Bromo-4-(2',4'-dichlorophenoxyethyl)-chromen-2-one (2g) :

Colorless crystals, yield 68%, m.p. 262–264 °C; ν_{\max} 1721 (C=O) cm⁻¹; δ_{H} 5.21 (2H, s, CH₂O), 6.80 (1H, s, C₃-H), 6.94–7.15 (6H, m, Ar-H) (Found : C, 47.91; H, 2.20. C₁₆H₉O₃BrCl₂ Calcd. : C, 48.04; H, 2.27%).

6-Methyl-4-(2',4',5'-trichlorophenoxyethyl)-chromen-2-one (3a) :

Colorless crystals, yield 82%, m.p. 238–240 °C; ν_{\max} 1709 (C=O) cm⁻¹; δ_{H} 2.50 (3H, s, C₆-CH₃), 5.53 (2H, s, CH₂O), 6.58 (1H, s, C₃-H), 7.33–7.89 (5H, m, Ar-H);

m/z (%) 368 (M⁺, 24), 370 (M⁺+2, 24), 372 (M⁺+4, 8), 374 (M⁺+6, 3) (Found : C, 55.09; H, 2.81. C₁₇H₁₁O₃Cl₃ Calcd. : C, 55.24; H, 3.00%).

7-Methyl-4-(2',4',5'-trichlorophenoxyethyl)-chromen-2-one (3b) :

Colorless crystals, yield 76%, m.p. 258–260 °C; ν_{\max} 1722 (C=O) cm⁻¹; δ_{H} 2.50 (3H, s, C₆-CH₃), 5.45 (2H, s, CH₂O), 6.57 (1H, s, C₃-H), 7.17–8.09 (5H, m, Ar-H) (Found : C, 55.11; H, 2.79. C₁₇H₁₁O₃Cl₃ Calcd. : C, 55.24; H, 3.00%).

1-(2,4',5'-Trichlorophenoxyethyl)-benzof[f]chromen-3-one (3c) :

Colorless crystals, yield 78%, m.p. 260–262 °C; ν_{\max} 1731 (C=O) cm⁻¹; δ_{H} 5.70 (2H, s, CH₂O), 6.78 (1H, s, C₃-H), 7.31–8.76 (8H, m, Ar-H) (Found : C, 59.07; H, 2.60. C₂₀H₁₁O₃Cl₃ Calcd. : C, 59.22; H, 2.73%).

4-(2',4',5'-Trichlorophenoxyethyl)-benzof[h]chromen-2-one (3d) :

Colorless crystals, yield 72%, m.p. 274–276 °C; ν_{\max} 1711 (C=O) cm⁻¹; δ_{H} 5.43 (2H, s, CH₂O), 6.80 (1H, s, C₃-H), 7.35–8.69 (8H, m, Ar-H) (Found : C, 59.06; H, 2.58. C₂₀H₁₁O₃Cl₃ Calcd. : C, 59.22; H, 2.73%).

6-Methoxy-4-(2',4',5'-trichlorophenoxyethyl)-chromen-2-one (3e) :

Colorless crystals, yield 71%, m.p. 237–239 °C; ν_{\max} 1720 (C=O) cm⁻¹; δ_{H} 3.87 (3H, s, C₆-OCH₃), 5.22 (2H, s, CH₂O), 6.74 (1H, s, C₃-H), 7.70–7.53 (5H, m, Ar-H) (Found : C, 52.78; H, 2.68. C₁₇H₁₁O₄Cl₃ Calcd. : C, 52.95; H, 2.88%).

6-Chloro-4-(2',4',5'-trichlorophenoxyethyl)-chromen-2-one (3f) :

Colorless crystals, yield 60%, m.p. 225–227 °C; ν_{\max} 1722 (C=O) cm⁻¹; δ_{H} 5.21 (2H, s, CH₂O), 6.87 (1H, s, C₃-H), 7.73–7.56 (5H, m, Ar-H) (Found : C, 49.09; H, 1.92. C₁₆H₈O₃Cl₄ Calcd. : C, 49.27; H, 2.07%).

6-Bromo-4-(2',4',5'-trichlorophenoxyethyl)-chromen-2-one (3g) :

Colorless crystals, yield 66%, m.p. 215–217 °C; ν_{\max} 1726 (C=O) cm⁻¹; δ_{H} 5.22 (2H, s, CH₂O), 6.80 (1H, s, C₃-H), 7.13–7.69 (5H, m, Ar-H) (Found : C, 44.09; H, 1.72. C₁₆H₈O₃BrCl₃ Calcd. : C, 44.23; H, 1.86%).

4-(4'-Bromophenoxyethyl)-6-methylchromen-2-one (4a) :

Colorless crystals, yield 88%, m.p. 218–220 °C; ν_{\max} 1715 (C=O) cm⁻¹; δ_{H} 2.43 (3H, s, C₆-CH₃), 5.19 (2H, s, CH₂O), 6.62 (1H, s, C₃-H), 6.86–7.44 (7H, m, Ar-H); *m/z* (%) 344 (M⁺, 36), 346 (M⁺+2, 36) (Found : C,

58.98; H, 3.61. $C_{17}H_{13}O_3Br$ Calcd. : C, 59.15; H, 3.80%.

4-(4'-Bromophenoxymethyl)-7-methylchromen-2-one (4b) :

Colorless crystals, yield 72%, m.p. 170–172 °C; ν_{max} 1715 (C=O) cm^{-1} ; δ_H 2.45 (3H, s, C_6-CH_3), 5.13 (2H, s, CH_2O), 6.55 (1H, s, C_3-H), 6.85–7.44 (7H, m, Ar-H) (Found : C, 58.92; H, 3.66. $C_{17}H_{13}O_3Br$ Calcd. : C, 59.15; H, 3.80%).

1-(4'-Bromophenoxymethyl)-benzo[ff]chromen-3-one (4c) :

Colorless crystals, yield 63%, m.p. 205–207 °C; ν_{max} 1712 (C=O) cm^{-1} ; δ_H 5.17 (2H, s, CH_2O), 6.64 (1H, s, C_3-H), 6.87–7.44 (10H, m, Ar-H) (Found : C, 62.79; H, 3.29. $C_{20}H_{13}O_3Br$ Calcd. : C, 63.01; H, 3.44%).

4-(4'-Bromophenoxymethyl)-benzo[h]chromen-2-one (4d) :

Colorless crystals, yield 68%, m.p. 252–254 °C; ν_{max} 1710 (C=O) cm^{-1} ; δ_H 5.24 (2H, s, CH_2O), 6.72 (1H, s, C_3-H), 6.89–8.60 (10H, m, Ar-H) (Found : C, 62.82; H, 3.33. $C_{20}H_{13}O_3Br$ Calcd. : C, 63.01; H, 3.44%).

4-(4'-Bromophenoxymethyl)-6-methoxychromen-2-one (4e) :

Colorless crystals, yield 52%, m.p. 201–203 °C; ν_{max} 1721 (C=O) cm^{-1} ; δ_H 3.88 (3H, s, C_6-OCH_3), 5.58 (2H, s, CH_2O), 6.88 (1H, s, C_3-H), 6.89–8.11 (7H, m, Ar-H) (Found : C, 56.37; H, 3.44. $C_{17}H_{13}O_4Br$ Calcd. : C, 56.53; H, 3.63%).

4-(4'-Bromophenoxymethyl)-6-chlorochromen-2-one (4f) :

Colorless crystals, yield 56%, m.p. 206–208 °C; ν_{max} 1731 (C=O) cm^{-1} ; δ_H 5.16 (2H, s, CH_2O), 6.68 (1H, s, C_3-H), 6.87–7.53 (7H, m, Ar-H) (Found : C, 52.41; H, 2.60. $C_{16}H_{10}O_3BrCl$ Calcd. : C, 52.56; H, 2.76%).

6-Bromo-4-(4'-bromophenoxymethyl)-chromen-2-one (4g) :

Colorless crystals, yield 58%, m.p. 212–214 °C; ν_{max} 1720 (C=O) cm^{-1} ; δ_H 5.28 (2H, s, CH_2O), 6.67 (1H, s, C_3-H), 6.99–7.87 (7H, m, Ar-H); m/z (%) 408 (M^+ , 28), 410 ($M^+ + 2$, 56), 412 ($M^+ + 4$, 28) (Found : C, 46.67; H, 2.29. $C_{16}H_{10}O_3Br_2$ Calcd. : C, 46.86; H, 2.46%).

6-Methyl-4-(2',4',6'-tribromophenoxymethyl)-chromen-2-one (5a) :

Colorless crystals, yield 83%, m.p. 238–240 °C; ν_{max} 1721 (C=O) cm^{-1} ; δ_H 2.50 (3H, s, C_6-CH_3), 5.29 (2H, s, CH_2O), 6.67 (1H, s, C_3-H), 7.35–8.03 (5H, m, Ar-H); m/z (%) 500 (M^+ , 6), 502 ($M^+ + 2$, 18), 504 ($M^+ + 4$,

18), 506 ($M^+ + 6$, 6) (Found : C, 40.41; H, 2.02. $C_{17}H_{11}O_3Br_3$ Calcd. : C, 40.59; H, 2.20%).

7-Methyl-4-(2',4',6'-tribromophenoxymethyl)-chromen-2-one (5b) :

Colorless crystals, yield 80%, m.p. 201–203 °C; ν_{max} 1720 (C=O) cm^{-1} ; δ_H 2.46 (3H, s, C_6-CH_3), 5.16 (2H, s, CH_2O), 6.80 (1H, s, C_3-H), 7.09–8.01 (5H, m, Ar-H) (Found : C, 40.43; H, 2.01. $C_{17}H_{11}O_3Br_3$ Calcd. : C, 40.59; H, 2.20%).

1-(2',4',6'-Tribromophenoxymethyl)-benzo[ff]chromen-3-one (5c) :

Colorless crystals, yield 83%, m.p. 260–262 °C; ν_{max} 1715 (C=O) cm^{-1} ; δ_H 5.63 (2H, s, CH_2O), 7.75 (1H, s, C_3-H), 7.57–8.08 (8H, m, Ar-H) (Found : C, 44.39; H, 1.95. $C_{20}H_{11}O_3Br_3$ Calcd. : C, 44.57; H, 2.06%).

4-(2',4',6'-Tribromophenoxymethyl)-benzo[h]chromen-2-one (5d) :

Colorless crystals, yield 81%, m.p. 220–222 °C; ν_{max} 1722 (C=O) cm^{-1} ; δ_H 5.28 (2H, s, CH_2O), 6.94 (1H, s, C_3-H), 7.25–8.61 (8H, m, Ar-H) (Found : C, 44.38; H, 1.97. $C_{20}H_{11}O_3Br_3$ Calcd. : C, 44.57; H, 2.06%).

6-Methoxy-4-(2',4',6'-tribromophenoxymethyl)-chromen-2-one (5e) :

Colorless crystals, yield 75%, m.p. 258–260 °C; ν_{max} 1727 (C=O) cm^{-1} ; δ_H 3.85 (3H, s, C_6-OCH_3), 5.19 (2H, s, CH_2O), 6.80 (1H, s, C_3-H), 7.06–7.75 (5H, m, Ar-H) (Found : C, 39.14; H, 2.02. $C_{17}H_{11}O_4Br_3$ Calcd. : C, 39.34; H, 2.14%).

6-Chloro-4-(2',4',6'-tribromophenoxymethyl)-chromen-2-one (5f) :

Colorless crystals, yield 70%, m.p. 248–250 °C; ν_{max} 1720 (C=O) cm^{-1} ; δ_H 5.24 (2H, s, CH_2O), 6.80 (1H, s, C_3-H), 7.36–7.87 (5H, m, Ar-H) (Found : C, 36.57; H, 1.43. $C_{16}H_8O_3Br_3Cl$ Calcd. : C, 36.72; H, 1.54%).

6-Bromo-4-(2',4',6'-tribromophenoxymethyl)-chromen-2-one (5g) :

Colorless crystals, yield 74%, m.p. 242–244 °C; ν_{max} 1715 (C=O) cm^{-1} ; δ_H 5.19 (2H, s, CH_2O), 6.83 (1H, s, C_3-H), 7.28–7.83 (5H, m, Ar-H) (Found : C, 33.63; H, 1.28. $C_{16}H_8O_3Br_4$ Calcd. : C, 33.84; H, 1.42%).

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